

How to use Mendeley reference manager?

Mendeley reference manager is a very good and easy to handle application to manage your references and the PDF reprints stored on your computer.

However, it took me several hours to figure out how the manager works and the different tools you need are interconnected.

What you need:

1. A personal Elsevier account (www.elsevier.com/products/mendeley
It's easy to get - you will be guided when you install Mendeley reference manager on your computer)
2. Mendeley reference manager on your computer (*It's very comfortable to create a database with all the references already stored on your computer; [Mendeley Reference Manager | Mendeley](#)*)
3. Mendeley cite (Plugin for Microsoft Word; [Mendeley Cite | Mendeley](#))
4. Mendeley online application ([Mendeley Reference Manager](#))

*The **Mendeley cite** plugin will only work with the **Mendeley online database** you have to create independently from the **Mendeley reference manager database on your computer!** You´ll have to interchange references between your computer and the online application best by exporting a BibTex library (*.bib, Export function of the **Mendeley reference manager**) and importing to your **Mendeley reference manager online application**. All **collections** you create in the online application will be available in **Mendeley cite** of your Word text processor. **The collections created on your computer by the reference manager will not be assessable.***